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ABSTRACTS

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***Subhiksha Keralam* - Pulse Crops in Kerala's Summer Rice Fallows**

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Rice-rice-fallow is the most common rice-based farming technique in northern Kerala, particularly in Kasaragod, Kannur, and Kozhikode districts. A field research was carried out at the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pilicode, Kerala, India, to ascertain the suitability of several pulse crops (cowpea, black gram, green gram and red gram) for summer fallows of double-cropped lowland rice fields under changing nitrogen doses. The following factors were significant for cowpea: crop growth rate (CGR) (4.57 g m⁻² per day), yield at 50% RDN (1681.16 kg ha⁻¹), leaf area index (LAI) at 100% and 50% RDN (1.16 and 1.28 respectively), and number of branches per plant at 100% and 75% recommended dose of nutrients (RDN) (9.40 and 9.93 respectively). Cowpea and red gram fared better than the other pulses regarding yield.

Keywords: sustainability; fallow; pulse; *Subhiksha Keralam*, lowland, rice; summer crop